

SHORT NOTES

NEW ROUTE FOR THE PREPARATION OF 3-HYDROXYCYCLO- HEXANEMETHANOL

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Von den Velden (*J. prakt. Chem.*, 1877, 15, 165) first prepared *m*-hydroxybenzyl alcohol by the reduction of *m*-hydroxybenzoic acid with sodium amalgam. Mettler (*Ber.*, 1905, 38, 1752) obtained the same alcohol in 45% yield by following the above method.

Lapworth and Showsmith (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 1395) improved the yield to 80% by the reduction of *m*-hydroxybenzaldehyde with sodium amalgam. The present author has obtained the product in 82% yield by an alternative method, involving the reduction of *m*-hydroxybenzaldehyde with lithium aluminium hydride.

The preparation of 3-hydroxycyclohexanemethanol (stereoisomers), and that of *cis*- and *trans*-diol, separately, have been reported by different authors from 3-hydroxycyclohexane carboxylic acid and its derivatives (Clark and Owen, *ibid.*, 1950, 2103; Goering and Serres, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 5908; Noyce and Denny, *ibid.*, p. 5912; 1954, 76, 769; Parkin and Tattershall, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, 91, 480).

The present work describes the devised method for the preparation of 3-hydroxybenzyl alcohol and its hydrogenation at room temperature and pressure over platinum oxide catalyst to 3-hydroxycyclohexanemethanol.

The attempted method for the hydrogenation of 3-hydroxybenzyl alcohol over Raney nickel catalyst was not successful as the resultant product was mostly *m*-cresol.

m-Hydroxybenzyl Alcohol (II).—*m*-Hydroxybenzaldehyde (25 g.), dissolved in ether (300 c.c.), was added dropwise to a gently refluxing solution of LiAlH_4 (5 g.) in ether (500 c.c.) in a three-necked flask, fitted with a mercury-sealed stirrer and condenser (CaCl_2 -guard tube). The reaction mixture was allowed to reflux for 3 hours,

cooled in ice and the excess LiAlH_4 was destroyed by dropwise addition of ice-cold water. The precipitated inorganic hydroxides were dissolved by the dropwise addition of ice-cold 10% H_2SO_4 . The mixture was extracted with ether and the ether extract washed with sodium bisulphite solution to remove the unchanged aldehyde, followed by sodium bicarbonate and finally water to remove the acid completely.

The ether extract was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the solvent removed. The residue was recrystallised from benzene, yield 20.5 g. (82%), m.p. $68.5-69^\circ$ (lit. 67.73°). (Found: C, 77.52; H, 7.52. Calc. for $\text{C}_7\text{H}_8\text{O}$: C, 77.77; H, 7.40%).

Attempted Hydrogenation of (II).—*m*-Hydroxybenzyl alcohol (50 g.) was dissolved in a solution of NaOH (15 g. in 50 c.c. water) and the volume made up to 95 c.c. with water. Raney nickel catalyst (6 g.) was then added and the mixture hydrogenated at 150° and 238 mm for 2 hours. The cooled, filtered and acidified solution was extracted with ether and after drying over anhydrous sodium sulphate, the ether was removed. The product was crude *m*-cresol (V), confirmed by the preparation and combustion analysis of the nitro (m.p. $102-103.5^\circ$) and bromo (m.p. $82-83^\circ$) derivatives.

3-Hydroxycyclohexanemethanol.—To the alcohol (II, 5 g.), dissolved in ethanol (50 c.c.), platinum oxide catalyst (0.15 g.) was added and the mixture hydrogenated for 40 hours, during which period the theoretically required volume of hydrogen was absorbed. The catalyst was removed by filtration and the solvent by distillation under reduced pressure. The residue was distilled *in vacuo*, yield 4.5 g. (81%); b.p. $115-20^\circ/0.5$ mm; n_D^{20} 1.4900 (lit. 1.4900). (Found: C, 64.40; H, 10.95. Calc. for $\text{C}_7\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2$: C, 64.60; H, 10.85%).

3-Hydroxycyclohexanemethyl chloride (IV) was prepared from (III) in 78% yield according to the method of Clark and Owen (*loc. cit.*), b.p. $125-35^\circ/30$ mm; n_D^{24} 1.4910 (lit. 1.4910). (Found: C, 56.26; H, 9.01; Cl, 23.5. Calc. for $\text{C}_7\text{H}_{13}\text{OCl}$: C, 56.56; H, 8.9; Cl, 23.8%).